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Histopathological Study of Prostatic Lesions in a Sample of Libyan Men

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ABSTRACT

Background: Prostate pathologies commonly encountered in men. The Benign lesions were more common compared to malignancies, both seen frequently with advancing age. Prostate cancer is the second most common cancer in the world with a higher prevalence in the developed countries. The aim of the current study is to identify the various prostatic lesions seen in prostate specimens, as well as correlating demographic information with histological results, in addition to grades prostate cancer using the modified Gleason grading system. **Materials and Methods:** A retrospective analytic study of prostatic samples received and diagnosed in pathology department at Sirte Oncology Centre from July 2021 to November 2022. **Results:** 37(64.9%) of analyzed cases were transurethral resection of prostate (TURP) specimens. The major affected age group of prostate pathologies is the 61 – 70 year cohort, where benign lesion is most commonly encountered 50 (87.7%) cases, and benign prostatic hyperplasia is the commonest benign histopathological diagnosis 49 (85.96 %) cases. Gleason grading showed that poorly differentiated carcinomas were the most common grade with the most common Gleason's score was found to be eight seen in 42.9 % cases, which falls into category Grade Group 4 of the new classification system. **Conclusion:** Benign lesions is the commonest encountered prostatic pathology particularly benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), commonly seen in the age group of 61 to 70 years. The Prostatic adenocarcinoma was common in the age group of 71-80 years. Histopathological evaluation plays important role in diagnosis and management of prostatic lesions.

1. Introduction

Prostate is one of the most commonly affected organ in the men, associated with significant morbidity and mortality¹. 105 million males globally in 2015 were reported with prostatic lesions². Growth and survival of prostatic cells being hormone (androgen) dependent¹. The

benign lesions, particularly benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), are even more common encountered urological illness in most studies³. Benign as well as malignant conditions are increasingly frequent with advancing age, and prostate enlargement has direct effect on urinary

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system^{4 5 6}. Together Laboratory investigations and histopathological evaluation play important role in diagnosis and management of both benign and malignant prostatic lesions present with similar clinical presentation. Thus, Prostatic biopsies, specimens from complete prostatectomy procedures, and prostatic chips from transurethral resection of prostate (TURP) specimen have become a significant workload for a pathologist⁷. Histopathological grading performed by Gleason scoring shown to correlate well with survival, thus used as an important prognostic indicator of prostate cancer⁸.

The aim of the current study was to determine the various prostatic lesions encountered in received prostate specimens, in addition to correlate the demographic data with histopathological findings and to grade prostate adenocarcinoma (PAC) according to the modified Gleason grading system.

2. Materials and Method

A retrospective study carried at pathology department of Sirte Oncology Centre from July 2021 to November 2022. The histopathological reports of 57 patients who underwent histopathological examination of their prostatic specimens included prostatic trucut biopsies, transurethral resection of prostate [TURP] chips, and open prostatectomy retrieved from the archive of histopathology department. The slides reviewed by the author to makes a consensus diagnosis and consensus scoring and group grading of adenocarcinoma cases, these to be

conformed to the current 5-tier system recommended by the International Society of Urological Pathology and adopted by the World Health Assembly in 2016, where Grade Group 1 includes all Gleason's score ≤ 6 , Grade Group 2 is Gleason's $3 + 4 = 7$, and Grade Group 3 is Gleason's $4 + 3 = 7$ whereas Grade Group 4 and 5 are Gleason's scores 8 and 9–10, respectively. The data regarding nature of specimen, age, diagnosis, and Gleason's scoring and group grading of the adenocarcinoma were collected.

3. Data analysis

The data was analyzed using SPSS version 24.0 statistical software, where descriptive statistics of qualitative variables, the frequency distribution procedure was run, as well as some distributions in relation to the age groups were performed with calculation of both the number of cases and percentages and for descriptive statistics of quantitative variables, the mean, median and range were used to describe central tendency and dispersion.

4. Results

Total 57 cases were evaluated with age ranging from 45 to 87 years and the mean age at time of diagnosis was 70.28 years. Most common age group of the studied cases of prostatic diseases were aged between 61 and 70 years accounting 21(36.8%) of all cases. The age related distribution of all prostatic lesions is demonstrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Age specific distribution of prostatic lesions for all cases(N=57)

S.no.	Age in years	No. of cases (%)
1	40-50	2(3.5)
2	51-60	8(14.0)
3	61-70	21(36.8)
4	71-80	19(33.3)
5	>80	7(12.3)

The majority of the 57 reported prostatic surgical specimens were transurethral resection of prostate [TURP] specimens 37(64.9%), followed by 15(26.3%) of open prostatectomies, and 5 (8.8%) of trucut needle biopsies as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Distribution of cases in relation to surgical biopsy specimens (N=57)

Surgical biopsy specimens	No. of cases (%)
Transurethral resection of the prostate	37(64.9)
Trucut needle biopsy	5(8.8)
Open prostatectomy	15(26.3)

Benign lesions were more common compared to malignancies. Out of 57 cases, 50 (87.7%) cases were benign. Benign prostatic hyperplasia was the most common encountered benign histopathological diagnosis 49 (85.96 %) cases; the benign lesions included one case (1.8 %) BPH alone, 39(68.4%) cases of BPH with chronic active inflammation and 9(15.8 %) cases of BPH with chronic inflammation and one case (1.8%) of

granulomatous inflammation. No other prostatic lesions such as high grade PIN or low grade PIN, atypical adenomatoid hyperplasia or xanthogranulomatous prostatitis reported. There were seven malignant lesions, diagnosed as adenocarcinoma of prostate comprising of 12.3 % of studied cases (Table 3), and were graded using Gleason's scoring.

Table 3. Distribution of final histopathological diagnosis in relation to age

Age group	No. of benign cases N (%)				No. of Malignant cases N (%)
	BPH*	BPH* with chronic active inflammation	BPH* with chronic inflammation	Chronic granulomatous inflammation	PAC*
40-50	0	2(3.5 %)	0	0	0
51-60	0	5(8.8 %)	1(1.8%)	0	2(3.5 %)
61-70	0	18(31.6 %)	1(1.8%)	1(1.8%)	1(1.8%)
71-80	1(1.8%)	10(17.5 %)	5(8.8 %)	0	3(5.3%)
>80	0	4(7%)	2(3.5 %)	0	1(1.8%)
Total	1(1.8%)	39 (68.4%)	9(15.8%)	1(1.8%)	7(12.3%)
	50(87.7)				7(12.3)

N=57, BPH*: Benign prostatic hyperplasia, PAC*: Prostatic adenocarcinoma.

Gleason grading showed that poorly differentiated carcinomas were the most common grade (n = 5, 71.4 %), whereas the rest were moderately differentiated (n = 2, 28.6%). The Gleason scores in the adenocarcinoma cases ranged from 7 to 9

(Grade Group 2-5 in the ISUP recommended system) with the most common Gleason's score was found to be 8 seen in (42.9 %) cases which falls into category Grade Group 4 of the new classification system (Table 4).

Table 4. Grade group of prostatic adenocarcinoma cases

Grade Group	No. of cases (%)
Grade Group 1	0(0)
Grade Group2	1(14.3)
Grade Group3	1(14.3)
Grade Group4	3(42.9)
Grade Group 5	2(28.6)

N= 7 cases

5. Discussion

In the current study, mean age for all 57 prostate cases was 70.28 years with a range of 45-87 years. This was comparable with results of Deshpande et al (mean age 67.84, n=63), Lakhey et al (mean 67.61, n=91), Vani et al (mean age 63.9), Javed R et al, Jayapradeep et al and Banerjee et al (most cases in age group 61-70 years)^{9 10 11 12 13}.

Interestingly, most of received surgical specimens were TURP chips as indicated in Table 2, accounting for 37(64.9%) of total specimens, as it is a simple procedure recommended for treatment of BPH. Our findings were in an agreement with other studies^{14 15}.

In our study, majority of patients was diagnosed with prostatic pathologies between 61-70 years followed by the age group of 71 to 80 years, in accordance with other studies^{14 16}, with maximum cases reported with benign lesions 50(87.7%) and 7(12.3%) with prostatic adenocarcinoma, which is consistent with studies conducted by Garalla et al who showed that 82% of cases were BPH and 18% PAC and Muthuvel et al who showed that 92.98% of cases were of BPH followed by 7.02% of PAC cases^{14 17}. Both pathologies increased in frequency with increased age as shown in other researches^{14 18 19}.

Regarding the distribution of benign prostatic lesions, the present study showed that, the benign cases included a single (1.8 %) case BPH alone, 39(68.4%) cases of BPH with chronic active inflammation and 9(15.8 %) cases of BPH with chronic inflammation and a single (1.8%) case of granulomatous inflammation in concordance with other observations^{20 21 22}

^{10 13 23}. Gleason grading system is one of the most powerful prognostic predictors in prostate cancer, it is crucial for a patient's prognosis and therapeutic options. However, this system has undergone significant revisions to enhance the prognostic and therapeutic values of the diagnostic investigations^{24 25}. In our study, a significant percentage (42.9%) of the adenocarcinomas fall within the Grade Group 4 category (encompassing the previous Gleason scores 8), our observation is inconsistent with other study done in Nigeria found the category Grade Group 1 to be the commonest¹⁶. The

prognostic value of this scoring system in our center requires further study for a longer period to analyzing more cases for better evaluation.

6. Conclusion

Trans Urethral Resection of Prostate specimens representing the commonest encountered specimen among all received and studied surgical specimens. Most prostatic lesions studied were found in the sixth to the seventh decade. Benign lesions is the commonest encountered prostatic pathology particularly benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) with or without inflammation while poorly differentiated adenocarcinoma is the predominant prostatic malignancy in our study.

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9. Competing interests

Authors declare that there are no competing interests with others.

10. References

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